

Five new Iberian Neomeniamorpha (Mollusca, Solenogastres)

Cinco nuevas especies Ibéricas de Neomeniamorpha (Mollusca, Solenogastres)

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ABSTRACT

Solenogastres belonging to the order Neomeniamorpha, recorded from off Galicia (Galicia Bank, NW Spain) at 752-769 m and from off the Azores at 1200-1240 m, are treated. This material was collected during the Spanish campaigns "Fauna Ibérica II" and "Cangrexo I" as well as during the French programme "Biaçores". The investigation of the ten specimens resulted in the discovery of five species new to science, described here as *Hemimenia glandulosa* sp.n., *H. atlantica* sp.n. and *H. cyclomyata* sp.n. (Hemimeniidae), *Neomenia oscar* sp.n. and *N. simplex* sp.n. (Neomeniidae). These species are characterised and systematically compared. All representatives are small (5 mm or less) and belong to the fauna of the Eastern Atlantic bathyal, which has been poorly investigated so far from off the Iberian Peninsula.

RESUMEN

Se presentan Solenogastres del orden Neomeniamorpha recogidos durante las campañas españolas "Fauna Ibérica II" y "Cangrexo I" en la costa de Galicia en 752-769 m y durante el programa francés "Biaçores" cerca de las Azores en 1200-1240 m. La investigación de los diez individuos, de un tamaño máximo de 5 mm, resultó en el descubrimiento de cinco especies nuevas para la ciencia que se describen como *Hemimenia glandulosa* sp.n., *H. atlantica* sp.n., *H. cyclomyata* sp.n. (Hemimeniidae), *Neomenia oscar* sp.n. y *N. simplex* sp.n. (Neomeniidae). Estas son caracterizadas y comparadas sistemáticamente. Pertenecen a la fauna batial del Atlántico oriental que todavía se ha investigado escasamente frente a la Península Ibérica.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Solenogastres, new species, distribution

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Solenogastres, nuevas especies, distribución geográfica

INTRODUCTION

Within the Mollusca, the conservative level of organisation is represented by the aplacophoran configuration, externally characterized by a mantle with a chitinous cuticle and unicellularly produced aragonitic sclerites. This level, the paraphyletic *Aplacophora*, is

represented today by two clades, the Solenogastres and the Caudofoveata (SALVINI-PLAWEN AND STEINER, 1966; HASZPRUNAR, 2000; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2003). Both classes have survived along their evolutionary pathways by adapting to a particular mode of life and by

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acquiring their respective characters (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1985). The Solenogastres (neomeniomorphs) have narrowed their body to glide over fairly firm substrates with the cilia of their restricted pedal groove, feeding as carnivores predominantly on Cnidaria. They are purely marine, hermaphroditic animals measuring from 0.8 mm to 30 cm and are known from depths of 1-6850 m. The class currently includes about 240 nominal species, a number that clearly underestimates their true biodiversity, as also documented by the present contribution.

The species of the class are grouped – based largely on the morphology of the mantle cover, the radula, and the foregut glandular organs – into 23 families within four orders (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978, 1985). Among them, the members of the order Neomeniamorpha represent a well-established monophyletic group characterised by their mantle sclerites, a mostly stoutish body shape and a highly complex accessory genital apparatus. They currently include 20 species classified as Hemimeniidae with the genera *Archaeomenia* (2 species) and *Hemimenia* (2 species), as well

as Neomeniidae with the single genus *Neomenia* (16 species) (see SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND URGORRI, 2003; SALVINI-PLAWEN AND PAAR-GAUSCH, 2004).

The present material was collected mainly during investigations related to the Iberian fauna and comes from off the northwestern coast of Galicia, Spain, specifically from one sampling site each of the Spanish project “Fauna Ibérica II” and another one of the campaign “Cangrexo I” carried out by the University of Santiago de Compostela. An additional sampling site was off the Azores from the French campaign “Biacores”. All ten specimens recorded presented a similar, stoutish body shape of 1.5-5 mm in size (Fig. 8), and were looking fairly alike except for the presence of a mid-dorsal keel in six individuals. This suggested at first only two separate species, but turned out to represent five organisationally different species new to science. Considering the limited geographic scope, this underlines the fragmentary knowledge of the Solenogastres fauna in general and of the regional species diversity in particular.

DESCRIPTIONS

Ordo NEOMENIAMORPHA Salvini-Plawen, 1978

Familia HEMIMENIIDAE Salvini-Plawen, 1978

Neomeniamorpha with thin cuticle, generally without epidermal papillae, sclerites as scales and solid spicules, short harpoon-shaped sclerites present;

radula polyserial or lacking, without ventral foregut glandular organs; spawning ducts without glandular caecum or associated gland.

Genus *Hemimenia* Nierstrasz, 1902

Type species: *Hemimenia intermedia* Nierstrasz, 1902

Definition: Solenogastres-Hemimeniidae without radula, with common

atrio-buccal opening; terminal sense organ and respiratory organs present.

Hemimenia glandulosa spec. nov. (Figs 1, 4-7)

Material examined: A single specimen of 3 mm length collected at type locality off Galicia/Spain. After examination of sclerites, ribbons of semithin serial sections (cs 2 µm) were made with a glass

Figures 1-3. Mantle sclerites (see text). 1: *Hemimenia glandulosa* n. sp.; 2: *Hemimenia atlantica* n. sp.; 3a-d: *Hemimenia cyclomyata* n. sp.; e, f: mantle sclerites of juvenile in same sample. Scale bars 30 µm.

Figuras 1-3. Escleritos del manto (véase texto). 1: Hemimenia glandulosa n. sp.; 2: Hemimenia atlantica n. sp.; 3a-d: Hemimenia cyclomyata; e, f: escleritos del manto de un juvenil de la misma muestra. Escalas 30 µm.

blade and stained by Richardson's solution. Holotype: Banco de Galicia/Spain, Fauna Ibérica II Sta. 173A (28.06.1991): 42° 42.37' - 42° 43.00' N, 11° 47.87' - 11° 45.78' W; 760-769 m. 3 mm (section series on slides), Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (Madrid) no. 15.05/46695

Derivatio nominis: Latin *glandula* = gland, *-osus* = rich presence of something; referring to the accumulation of glands in the genito-pallial region.

Diagnosis: Body rather stout, up to 3 mm x 0.9 mm, with distinct dorsomedian keel. Four types of calcareous mantle sclerites, the elongate blade-shaped solid sclerites being diagnostic; one pedal fold, extending into mantle cavity; cerebral connectives separate; pharynx with two regions; with seminal vesicle halfway down the length of pericardioducts, with receptacula seminis;

spawning ducts with unpaired terminal tube; a pair of two copulatory stylets each; accumulation of peri-pallial glands as well as of glands around genital tube; with about 7 pre-pallial spines on each side; respiratory organs as four stoutish folds.

Mantle: The mantle epithelium (10 µm thick) includes several glands, large glands are especially accumulated

subepidermally in the keel. The cuticle is 10-15 μm thick. There are four types of sclerites (Fig. 1): small elongate scales as the main type with the basal and lateral rims reinforced, 20 x 6 μm to 40 x 10 μm in size (Fig. 1a); interspersed elongate blade-shaped scales, 45 x 5 μm to 75 x 10 μm in size (Fig. 1b); keel with short harpoon-shaped sclerites, 40-60 μm in length (Fig. 1c); elongate straight scales, 60 x 5 μm , along the pedal groove (Fig. 1d). Alongside the end of the pedal groove, at least seven pre-pallial spines are present on each side (Fig. 7).

Foot and mantle cavity: The pedal ciliary pit is small and, posteriorly, sickle-shaped. The roof forms one strong pedal fold which diminishes terminally but ends shortly before the mantle cavity. The voluminous pedal glands, packed into follicles, occupy the periphery of anterior body cavity and open frontally as well as laterally into the pit. They are palely stained and histologically different from the singular, finely granulated and strongly stained

sole glands; these open dorsally into the pit and subsequently along the entire pedal groove, also entering the pedal fold.

The mantle cavity is narrow and, behind the anus, largely filled by four rather stout longitudinal respiratory folds. Anteriorly, the copulatory stylets open at the beginning of the cavity, which forms a ciliated, flattened rostral pouch receiving dorsally the secondary genital opening (Fig. 7) and continuing a little further as a tube (Fig. 6). The entire space surrounding the posterior mantle cavity and dorso-laterally the rectum is densely filled by distinctly granulated gland cells (gl₁); the central space between rectum and terminal spawning ducts with their unpaired outleading tube (and ventro-lateral to this) is occupied by another mass of fairly unstained glands (gl₂) which open together with the secondary genital tube into the flattened pallial pouch Figs 5-7).

Musculature: The epidermis is underlain by a thick layer of structureless,

(Right page) Figures 4-7. *Hemimenia glandulosa* n. sp. 4: Organisation of the anterior body; 5: organisation of the posterior body; 6: cross section in posterior body just anterior to fusion of spawning ducts; 7: cross section in posterior body just anterior to opening of spawning duct tube into pouch of pallial cavity.

Abbreviations, ao: atrial sense organ; ba: bag-like enlargement of connection between copulatory stylet gland and spawning duct; co: suprarectal commissure; cs: copulatory stylets; csg: copulatory stylet gland; csgd: looped duct of copulatory stylet gland into stylet sheath; fo: pedal fold (foot); gb: buccal ganglion; gc: cerebral ganglion; gl₁ and gl₂: accumulation of different glands (see text); go: gonad; gs: ground substance (matrix); gv: ventral ganglion; hg: hindgut; ma: mantle; mg: midgut; mu: musculature; nsl: lateral nerve cord; pc: pericardium; pd: pericardioduct; ph: pharynx; po: anterior pouch of pallial cavity; ro: respiratory organs; rs: receptaculum seminis; sd: spawning duct; sp: pre-pallial spines; to: dorso-terminal sense organ; vs: vesicula seminalis.

(Página derecha) Figuras 4-7. *Hemimenia glandulosa* n. sp. 4: Organización de la parte anterior del cuerpo; 5: organización de la parte posterior del cuerpo; 6: corte en la parte posterior del cuerpo, justo delante del confluente de los conductos eferentes de gametos; 7: corte en la parte posterior del cuerpo justo delante de la abertura de los conductos eferentes de gametos en la bolsa de la cavidad paleal.

Abreviaturas, ao: órgano sensorial del atrio; ba: ensanchamiento sacciforme de la conexión entre la glándula del estilete copulatorio y el conducto eferente de gametos; co: comisura suprarectal; cs: estiletes copulatorios; csg: glándula del estilete copulatorio; csgd: conducto en bucle de la glándula del estilete copulatorio hacia la vaina del estilete; fo: pliegue del pie; gb: ganglio bucal; gc: ganglio cerebral; gl₁ and gl₂: acumulación de distintas glándulas (véase texto); go: gónada; gs: sustancia de fondo (matriz); gv: ganglio ventral; hg: digestivo posterior; ma: manto; mg: digestivo medio; mu: musculatura; nsl: cordón nervioso lateral; pc: pericardio; pd: pericardioducto; pb: faringe; po: bolsa anterior de la cavidad paleal; ro: órganos respiratorios; rs: receptaculum seminis; sd: conducto eferente de gametos; sp: espinas pre-paleales; to: órgano sensorial dorso-terminal; vs: vesícula seminalis.

pale-staining matrix or ground substance, 100-200 μm thick, reaching 250 μm in the keel (Figs 4-7). Without distinct inner musculature, the matrix is medially limited by the pedal or pharyngeal glands, the midgut and gonads, or posteriorly the accessory genital organs. Ventrally, a more distinct accumulation of longitudinal muscle fibres is present. The matrix is traversed by numerous lacunae containing hemocytes and by muscle fibres.

The dorsoventral bundles are weak but cause regular constrictions of the lateral midgut, forming serial pouches. Dorsally the bundles branch into fibres which lose themselves within the matrix. Below the gut, their fibres delimit the ventral sinus. More distinct musculature exists around the pharynx and as retractors of the copulatory stylets.

Sensory system: The fused cerebral ganglion (200 μm wide, 80 μm high, 90 μm long) antero-laterally gives off at least three pairs of nerves; the separate connectives emerge termino-laterally. Short lateral connectives (100 μm) extend to elongate lateral ganglia (80 μm x \varnothing 50 μm). First ventral ganglia (75 μm x \varnothing 65 μm) located behind pedal pit with two commissures; the globular buccal ganglia (\varnothing 50 μm) are in same region of cross sections. Ganglia posteriora superiora with 300 μm long medullary suprarectal commissure (\varnothing 30 μm) below end of pericardium.

The atrial or vestibular sense organ is delimited by a horseshoe-shaped ciliary tract; posteriorly, this tract curves as a paired fold dorsally, merging and ending at the posterior roof of the atrial cavity. Anteriorly the ciliary tracts form, by fusion, the roof of a small pre-atrial pit without sclerites and cilia, which is thus outside and ventro-frontally of the atrial cavity. The sensory area itself bears papillae bundled basally into up to eight organs.

The terminal sense organ is well differentiated at the rear of the body (Fig. 5).

Alimentary tract: The mouth behind the atrial ciliary tracts is provided with a

weak sphincter; there is no separate buccal area. The mouth leads to a strongly folded pharynx which, in its first section, shows loose circular, longitudinal and radial muscle fibres. Beginning with the buccal ganglia, the circular musculature in this second section (posterior to the expected position of the radula) is distinctly thickened (35-50 μm) extending up to or close to the more or less frontal opening into the midgut (Fig. 4). The pharynx is dorsally enlarged (bulge) near the buccal ganglia; here, the dorso-lateral epithelium is smooth and distinctly cuticularised. The entire foregut is provided with a thick coat of glandular cells, about 100 μm , with coarsely granulated contents. These cells open intercellularly into the pharynx lumen, particularly dense within the two dorso-lateral, cuticularised areas.

The midgut has a high epithelium and is laterally constricted into a regular series of pouches; it is provided throughout with a middorsal and in the posterior body also with a midventral ciliary tract. The lumen and midgut cells regularly include nematocysts (up to 40 μm long). The slender, ciliated rectum opens dorso-frontally into the mantle cavity.

Circulatory system: The entire heart is a middorsal invagination of the pericardium. The unpaired atrium extends frontally below the ventricle; there is one atrioventricular opening. The dorsal sinus runs in continuation of the heart closely above the gonopericardioducts and gonads. In the foregut region its course is ill-defined within the matrix. The ventral sinus in the usual position becomes indistinct in the pericardial region. In addition to granulocytes, at least one type of haemocyte appears to be present.

Reproductive system: The paired gonad contains eggs with a diameter up to 120 μm . The paired, slender gonopericardioducts open dorsally into the voluminous pericardium. The latter shows a paired antero-ventral enlargement, has anteriorly an overall ciliation, and posteriorly a latero-dorsal to ventro-lateral

ciliation; it contains sperm. The ciliated pericardioducts emerge laterally at the rear and enlarge after their proximal third, here also giving rise to a medial, empty seminal vesicle towards the rear (Figs 5 and 6). Their opening into the spawning ducts is nearly axially continuous with the emergence of the stalked, large receptaculum seminis (without sperm). The paired spawning ducts are provided with high glandular and ciliated cells, as usual for most Solenogastres and merge in the last third to become a ciliated "tube" with circular musculature (Figs. 5 and 7); this tube opens, accompanied by the mass of glands gl₂, from the dorsal part into the flattened rostral pouch of the pallial cavity (Fig. 7). Just before their fusion, each spawning duct receives the opening of a medial, bag-like sack with simple epithelium (Figs. 5 and 6, ba); this represents the interconnecting organ between the respective stylet gland outlet and the spawning duct. The stylet gland (also termed penis gland) is an elongate organ that extends along each side far anteriorly (Fig. 5). Its histology is qualitatively the same as the spawning ducts. At the posterior end, each gland continues into two ducts, a short one to the mentioned bag-like sack connecting the respective spawning duct and a long, slender and curved duct (thus being extensible) to the distal sheath of the copulatory stylets at its dorsal side (facing the solid spine). As is typical for neomeniamorphs, the copulatory stylets themselves consist of two elements at each side, a circular solid spine and below this a gutter-like element. Both apparatus are ventrally located and extend from a latero-ventral

position proximally to medio-ventrally within the mantle cavity. At each side, the two elements have, in their proximal portion, their own sheath, but are together surrounded by a common longitudinal musculature; more distally, at about two thirds of their extension, the sheaths fuse and both elements are merely separated by their own thin membrane of connective tissue. The common sheath at each side receives, further distally, below the position of the flattened mantle cavity pouch into a tube, the duct of the stylet gland. Both stylet apparatus end within the ventral mantle cavity.

Comparison: Two *Hemimenia* species are currently known: *Hemimenia intermedia* Nierstrasz from Indonesia and *H. dorsosulcata* Salvini-Plawen from the subantarctic Pacific (NIERSTRASZ, 1902; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978). *H. glandulosa* spec. nov. from the Galicia-Bank is distinguished from both species by the geographic provenance, by its small body size (*H. intermedia* = 14 mm, *H. dorsosulcata* = 30 mm), by the sclerites (60-65 µm long and finely striated scales in *H. intermedia*, *H. dorsosulcata* with interspersed 30-40 µm long club-shaped elements), by the unpaired terminal tube of the spawning ducts and by the two types of accumulated glands in the pre-pallial and pallial region respectively (according to Nierstrasz, in *H. intermedia* "a compact, dense tissue" is present which possibly refers to supra-pallial glands). In addition, *H. glandulosa* differs from *H. intermedia* in having two pharyngeal regions rather than a homogeneous muscular coat; from *H. dorsosulcata* in having a dorsomedian keel as well as vesiculae seminales.

Hemimenia atlantica spec. nov. (Figs 2, 8-14)

Material examined: Two specimens (holotype and paratype 2; Fig. 8) collected from off the Azores. One additional specimen (paratype 1) from off Galicia/Spain. After examination of sclerites, the holotype as well as paratype 1 from Galicia were cut in paraffin into serial sections (cs 10 µm) and Azan stained. Holotype: Azores, Campaign "Biaçores" Sta. 64 (14.11.1971): 38° 43' N, 28° 29' W; 1200-1240 m. 5 mm (serial sections on slides), Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Malacologie), Paris. Paratype 1: Banco "A Quiniela" off Galicia/Spain, Campaign "Cangrexo I" Sta. M-13, No. 01.281191-b (28.11.1991): 43° 27' 90" N, 09° 29' 19" W; 752 m. 3 mm (serial sections on slides),

Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, no. 15.05/46696). Paratype 2: Same sample as holotype, 3 mm (specimen in alcohol), Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Malacologie), Paris.
Derivatio nominis: Latin *atlanticus* = referring to the Atlantic Ocean.

Diagnosis: Body rather stout, up to 5 mm x 1.3 mm, with distinct dorsomedian keel. Five types of calcareous mantle sclerites; one pedal fold, ending before mantle cavity; cerebral connectives with separate origin; pharynx with two regions; with seminal vesicles and receptacula seminis; spawning ducts fuse at opening into genital pouch, which is almost separated from mantle cavity; at each side are two copulatory stylets, with about up to 10 pre-pallial spines on each side; accumulation of peri-pallial glands; accumulation of glands around genital pouch; respiratory organs as 6-7 stoutish folds.

Mantle: The mantle epidermis (9-12 μm thick) with several glands epithelially and subepithelially; large subepidermal glands are especially accumulated distally in the keel (Fig. 14). The cuticle 5-10 μm thick. There are five types of sclerites (Fig. 2): the two main types are small elongate scales 28 x 8 μm to 45 x 12 μm (Fig. 2a) and elongate, basally somewhat slenderizing scales, 40 x 11 μm to 65 x 7-8 μm (Fig. 2b), both with reinforced basal and lateral rims; interspersed, slender solid sclerites, 30 x 4 μm to 50 x 5 μm (Fig. 2c); keel with short harpoon-shaped sclerites, 38-55 μm in length (Fig. 2d); blade-shaped scales measuring 35-45 x 9-10 μm (Fig. 2e) along the pedal groove, two bundles

of 5-10 pre-pallial spines are present slightly in front of the opening of the genital pouch, one bundle at each side, positioned far apart (Fig. 12).

Foot and mantle cavity: The pedal ciliary pit is posteriorly sickle-shaped and its roof forms three folds, the median one entering the groove and ending with the opening of the genital pouch in front of the mantle cavity. Voluminous, palely stained pedal glands packed into follicles occupy the anterior body cavity up to the cerebral ganglion and open frontally as well as laterally into the pit. The sole glands along the pedal groove are less voluminous but qualitatively the same.

The mantle cavity is narrow, and behind the dorso-frontally opening anus it is largely filled by seven rather stout longitudinal folds. Anteriorly, the cavity is almost totally separated from the genital area by a tissue fold with transverse muscles (Fig. 10); the genital area is constricted into a folded rostral pouch with a small lumen. The spawning ducts open dorsally into this genital pouch (Fig. 13) and the copulatory stylets end within the pouch opening. Behind the secondary genital opening, the pouch is dorsally and laterally accompanied by transverse musculature which originates in the scattered body wall musculature and which runs into the fold separating the genital

(Right page) Figures 8-14. *Hemimenia atlantica* n.sp. 8: Specimen 3 mm long, anterior end at left (paratype 2); 9: organisation of the anterior body; 10: organisation of the posterior body; 11: cross section through atrial sense organ showing papillae with common trunk; 12: paratype 1, cross section in posterior body to show the one-sided double set of copulatory stylets; 13: cross section through posterior body in the opening of spawning duct(s) into pouch of pallial cavity; 14: cross section through pallial cavity.

Abbreviations as in Figures 4-7, egl: subepithelially arranged epidermal glands.

(Página derecha) Figuras 8-14. *Hemimenia atlantica* n.sp. 8: Especimen de 3 mm de longitud, extremidad anterior a la izquierda (paratipo 2); 9: organización de la parte anterior del cuerpo; 10: organización de la parte posterior del cuerpo; 11: corte del órgano sensorial del atrio mostrando papilas con un tronco compartido; 12: paratipo 1, corte en la parte posterior del cuerpo mostrando el conjunto unilateral de estiletes copulatorios; 13: corte en la parte posterior del cuerpo, a la altura de la abertura de los conductos eferentes de gametos en la bolsa de la cavidad paleal; 14: corte en la cavidad paleal.

Abreviaturas como en las Figuras 4-7, egl: glándulas epidérmicas en modo subepitelial.

pouch from the mantle cavity proper. The spaces surrounding the pouch and the terminal spawning ducts are occupied (at different densities) by fairly unstained glands (gl₂), each of which is distinctly surrounded by connective tissue and obviously opens into the pouch. The entire body space between the suprarectal commissure and the body end is densely filled by (suprapallial) gland cells (gl₁) of distinctly different quality and staining (Figs 10, 13, 14).

Musculature: The epidermis is underlain by a network of muscle fibres embedded in a structureless, pale-staining matrix up to 150 µm thick, dorsally (keel) up to 400 µm thick (Figs 9-10); there are no distinct layers except for a ventral accumulation of longitudinal muscle fibres. In the mid-body behind the pedal glands, this network is laterally and ventro-laterally condensed and set off from the gut, bridged by radial muscle fibres; more posteriorly, the matrix – consisting of a looser meshwork – is delimited by the internal organs.

The dorsoventral bundles are weak but cause regular constrictions of the lateral midgut, forming serial pouches. Below the gut, their fibres delimit the ventral sinus. A more distinct musculature is associated with the pharynx and the copulatory stylets.

Sensory system: The fused cerebral ganglion (250 µm wide, 85 µm high, 95 µm long) antero-laterally gives off at least two pairs of nerves; the separate connectives emerge termino-laterally. There are short lateral connectives (50 µm) extending to elongate, first lateral ganglia (125 µm x Ø 40 µm). The first ventral ganglia (55 µm x Ø 90 µm) lie behind the pedal pit and, proximally, their commissure gives off a pair of strong ventral nerves to the pit. The globular buccal ganglia (Ø 55 µm) are in the same region of the cross sections, lateral to the muscular coat of the pharynx (second region; Fig. 9). The most terminal of the lateral ganglia (ganglia posteriora superiora) are located below the beginning pericardioducts and show a 225-250 µm long, medullary suprarectal commissure (Ø 25 µm).

The atrial sense organ is delimited by a horseshoe-shaped ciliary tract; it curves posteriorly as a paired fold dorsally and ends abruptly; the small pre-atrial pit lacks sclerites or cilia and is folded. The sensory area itself bears long papillae, up to seven of which possess a common stalked trunk (Fig. 11).

There are five ventral pits in the same transverse region behind the mantle cavity opening; the central one might represent a terminal sense organ.

Alimentary tract: The narrow space between the posterior atrial ciliary tracts leads to the mouth; there is no real buccal cavity. The anterior pharynx shows a folded epithelium and is provided with a weak musculature; numerous subepithelial, long-stalked gland cells open intercellularly, with particular accumulation dorsally. After a short distance, behind the cerebral ganglion (above the pedal pit), the pharyngeal ring musculature is strengthened (up to 50-80 µm thick) and distinct radial muscle fibres are present. This condition (second region) continues on to the frontal opening into the midgut (Fig. 9). There are peripherally arranged granulated gland cells, apparently of the same quality as those of the first region. In addition, however, more scattered gland cells with granula are increasingly present towards the posterior side; they stain distinctly different by Azan. At each side, a muscle bundle originates from around the mouth opening to run alongside the pharynx to the body wall network above the beginning midgut.

The midgut with high epithelium is laterally constricted into regular pouches at distances of about 75 µm; it is provided throughout with a middorsal and in the posterior body also with a midventral ciliary tract. The lumen contained nematocysts. The slender, ciliated rectum opens dorso-frontally into the mantle cavity.

Circulatory system: The heart appears to be a middorsal invagination of the pericardium; due to the densely packed eggs throughout the pericardium and in the gonads, no details are visible in the holotype. Paratype 1 shows the

unpaired atrium continuing frontally into the ventricle. The dorsal sinus runs, in continuation of the heart, closely above the gonopericardi ducts and gonads. The ventral sinus in the usual position for the class becomes indistinct in the pericardial region. In addition to granulocytes ($\varnothing 8 \mu\text{m}$), a smaller type of haemocytes appears to be present.

Reproductive system: The paired gonad contains eggs with a diameter of up to $160 \mu\text{m}$; posteriorly, mature genital products cause the gonads to bulge into large pouches. The paired gonopericardi ducts continue dorsally into the voluminous pericardium, which bears a paired rostral pouch and is filled with mature eggs. The pericardi ducts emerge terminally; each possesses in its proximal course a small vesicula seminalis, differentiated medially and directed posteriorly (Fig. 10). At each side, a short-stalked, voluminous receptaculum seminis (without sperm) emerges latero-proximally from the spawning ducts. These latter ducts are paired throughout and fuse at their opening from dorsal into the flattened, rostrally directed genital pouch (Fig. 13). At a short distance before this opening, each spawning duct receives medially the terminally enlarged connecting duct from the respective stylet gland. Each of these is an elongate, twice-folded organ, in the holotype proximally surrounding the receptaculum (Fig. 10). Its histology is similar to the spawning ducts and it continues at the posterior end as two ducts, a short one to the respective spawning duct and a long, slender and

curved duct to the distal sheath of the copulatory stylet. The copulatory stylets are present on each side with two elements, a circular solid spine and below this a proximally flat element which becomes distally gutter-like. Both elements possess, halfway along their length, their own sheath surrounded by a common longitudinal musculature. Below the opening of the spawning ducts, each stylet gland duct opens from a latero-dorsal direction into the stylet sheath, which at this point is a common structure enclosing both elements. Both stylet apparatus end within the opening of the genital pouch. Paratype 1 (Galicia) shows at one side an additional, less extended set of copulatory stylets (Fig. 12).

Comparison: The general organisation of the present specimens of *Hemimenia atlantica* spec.nov. is in their general organisation fairly similar to *H. glandulosa* (above). Specific differences exist, however, in the length and shape of the interspersed slender sclerites (see Figs 1b and 2c), in the particular configuration of the two pharynx regions (thick circular musculature beginning here anteriorly to the expected position of the radula, in front of buccal ganglia, comp. Figures 4 and 9; glandular complement), and in the configuration of the terminal (paired) spawning ducts not differentiating an outleading "tube". *Hemimenia atlantica* differs from *H. intermedia* and *H. dorsosulcata* by the ventral opening of the spawning duct(s), otherwise by the same characters as in *H. glandulosa* (above).

Hemimenia cyclomyata spec. nov. (Figs 3, 15-19)

Material examined: Two specimens (holotype and a juvenile) collected from one sample off Galicia/Spain. Because the juvenile (2.1 mm length; Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, no. 15.05/46698, section series on slides) is classified within this species only with some reservations due to differences in its mantle sclerites, the description is focused on the holotype. After examination of sclerites, ribbons of semithin serial sections (cs $2 \mu\text{m}$) of both specimens were made with a glass blade and stained in Richardson's solution. Holotype: Banco de Galicia/Spain, Fauna Ibérica II Sta. 173A (28.06.1991): $42^{\circ} 42.37' - 42^{\circ} 43.00' \text{ N}$, $11^{\circ} 47.87' - 11^{\circ} 45.78' \text{ W}$; 760-769 m. 3.5 mm (section series on slides), Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (Madrid), no. 15.05/46697.

Derivatio nominis: Greek *kyklos* = ring; *mys, myos* = mouse, muscle; Latin *-atus* = provided with something; referring to the well-delimited pharynx constrictor.

Diagnosis: Body rather stout, 3.5 mm x 0.7 mm, with ill-defined dorsomedian keel. Calcareous mantle sclerites of four types, elongate paddle-shaped solid sclerites being diagnostic; one pedal fold, extending into mantle cavity; cerebral connectives separate; two regions of pharynx separated by a compact, strong muscle ring; no seminal vesicles, with receptacula seminis; spawning ducts paired throughout, opening by means of a common short cone; two copulatory stylets and about 6 pre-pallial spines on each side; without suprapallial glands, respiratory organs as ten stoutish folds.

Mantle: The dorsomedian area shows a somewhat unusual configuration: an irregularly defined keel composed of the ground substance (matrix) as well as of the heightened epithelium; keel regionally broad, of triangular or ill-defined form in cross section and enclosing grooves or pits. The 10-15 μm thick mantle epidermis contains scattered glands and is dorsomedially heightened to 20-40 μm . The cuticle is 10-15 μm thick, but may be dorsally thickened up to 40 μm . Some epidermal protrusions are visible but no true epidermis papillae are present. Four types of sclerites are present (Fig. 3): small elongate scales as the main type with the basal and lateral rims reinforced as well as distally somewhat pointed, 30 x 5 μm to 80 x 11 μm in size, the shorter ones being dominant (Fig. 3a); these are interspersed by the diagnostic, elongate paddle- to drop-like sclerites, dominant

middorsally, in two sizes of 50-90 x 8-12 μm (Fig. 3b) and 30-40 x 8 μm (Fig. 3c); the middorsal grooves/pits of the keel contain short harpoon-shaped sclerites that are 40-45 μm long (Fig. 3d). Some distance in front of the mantle cavity opening, at each side a ventro-posteriorly directed bundle of about 6 pre-pallial spines is present.

In the juvenile the paddle-like sclerites (Fig. 3b) reach a length of up to 120 μm and instead of the small elongate scales (Fig. 3a), a type of distally tapering scales (50-70 x 10-12 μm ; Fig. 3e) is present. In addition, rods (up to 110 μm long; Fig. 3f) are differentiated.

Foot and mantle cavity: The pedal ciliary pit is shallow and the roof forms a single fold that enters the groove and ends at the opening of the mantle cavity. Voluminous, palely stained pedal glands packed into follicles extend up to the cerebral ganglion and open frontally as well as laterally into the pit. Dorsally, long-necked sole glands which stain strongly and contain granules open next to one another into the pit. These distinctions contradict the opinion that both types of glands are merely different states of differentiation (e.g. HOFFMAN, 1949). Smaller sole glands continue along the pedal groove and open not only within the pedal fold but also within the lateral epithelium of the groove.

The mantle cavity bears a total of about 10 rather stout respiratory folds posteriorly and laterally. The anus opens dorsally in its anterior area;

(Right page) Figures 15-19. *Hemimenia cyclomyata* n. sp. 15: Organisation of the anterior body; 16: organisation of the posterior body; 17: cross section through anterior body in the region of the pharyngeal strong muscle ring; 18: cross section through anterior body in the region of the pharyngeal opening into the midgut; 19: cross section through beginning opening of pallial cavity.

Abbreviations as in Figures 4-7, bu: buccal cavity; cu: mantle cuticle; ep: mantle epithelium; mc: pallial cavity; op: opening "tube" of pharynx; pg₁ and pg₂: two different types of pedal gland cells. (Página derecha) Figuras 15-19. *Hemimenia cyclomyata* n. sp. 15: Organización de la parte anterior del cuerpo; 16: organización de la parte posterior del cuerpo; 17: Hemimenia cyclomyata n.sp., corte en la parte anterior del cuerpo en la región del fuerte anillo muscular faríngeo; 18: corte en la parte anterior del cuerpo en el paso de la faringe al digestivo medio; 19: corte al principio de la abertura de la cavidad paleal.

Abreviaturas como en las Figuras 4-7, bu: cavidad bucal; cu: cutícula del manto; ep: epitelio del manto; mc:cavidad paleal; op: abertura "tubo" de la faringe; pg₁ and pg₂: dos tipos distintos de células glandulares del pie.

ventro-anteriorly, the short cone of the secondary genital openings intrudes into the cavity (Fig. 19). The ventral space of the mantle cavity continues anteriorly beyond the cavity opening, thus forming a genital pouch. Posteriorly, this pouch houses the distal portions of the copulatory stylets and is overlain by the spawning ducts. There are no glands around the mantle cavity or in the area of the genital pouch.

Musculature: The circular and longitudinal fibres of the body wall musculature are loosely arranged and embedded in a structureless, pale-staining matrix that is relatively thin (25-50 μm thick, mid-dorsally up to 75 μm). Ventrally, the longitudinal muscle fibres are more numerous and more concentrated. Apart from the foregut musculature, there are radial fibres in (at least) the anterior region of the midgut, which runs some distance apart from the body wall.

The dorsoventral bundles are weak and cause no regular constrictions of the lateral (anterior) midgut. Below the gut, their fibres delimit the ventral sinus.

Sensory system: The fused cerebral ganglion flattens posteriorly (100-60 μm high, 180 μm wide, 75 μm long) and gives rise termino-laterally to the separate but closely adjoining connectives. Three pairs of cerebral nerves run to the atrial sense organ, each provided by a small initial ganglion; the two anterior pairs are integrated into the latero-frontal area of the cerebral ganglion and are delimited merely by their own tunica. The lateral connectives are short and strong (60 μm x \varnothing 15 μm); the first lateral ganglia are elongate (70 μm x \varnothing 25 μm). The first ventral ganglia (85 μm x \varnothing 70 μm) lie behind the pedal pit and have two commissures, the anterior one proximally giving off a pair of strong ventral nerves to the pit; the ganglia are immediately followed by the next pair. The buccal ganglia (\varnothing 55 μm) are in the same region of cross sections.

The nerve cords in the posterior body are almost medullar. In front of the genital pouch, each of the more prominent, elongate ganglia posteriora inferiora (\varnothing 30 μm) gives rise to a strong connective,

running between hindgut and spawning duct/stylet gland to the medullary lateral cord. The ganglia posteriora superiora (\varnothing 60 μm) below the beginning pericardiodycts are connected by a 130 μm long and medullary suprarectal commissure (\varnothing 30 μm ; Fig. 19).

The atrial sense organ is delimited by the horseshoe-shaped ciliary tract. It curves posteriorly as a paired fold dorsally and ends abruptly; the papilla of the sensory area, bundled up into groups of four, are not very densely arranged. There is no distinct pre-atrial area.

The terminal sense organ appears to be located somewhat subterminally at the body end (Fig. 16).

Alimentary tract: The alimentary tract begins ventrally with the buccal area in the common atriobuccal cavity, behind the posterior atrial ciliary tracts (Fig. 15). The buccal area has a low epithelium and ends in both individuals with a small circular fold (marking the internal mouth opening proper). The gut then continues with the widened anterior pharynx; this shows a folded epithelium, a few circular and longitudinal muscle bundles as well as distinct dorsal radial bundles. Unicellular, subepithelial pharyngeal gland cells are present. Midway along its length, the pharynx is surrounded by an obliquely running, compact muscle ring (constrictor; \varnothing 100-70 μm ; Figs. 15 and 17). Behind this the epithelium becomes high and interspersed with finger-like extended cells; these are underlain by a few circular and longitudinal muscle fibres as well as by a dense accumulation of coarsely granulated gland cells. The narrowed opening of the pharynx into the midgut is unusual: in both specimens it represents a short "tube" without sphincter (Fig. 18). The lower semicircular half of this tube consists of pharyngeal epithelium and the upper semicircular epithelium of very flat cells forming a thin roof over the thick-walled gutter.

The (anterior) midgut is distinctly separated from the body wall and shows poorly pronounced pouchings at distances of about 50 μm . A middorsal ciliary tract is present. The ciliated

rectum opens dorso-frontally into the mantle cavity

Reproductive system: The paired gonad lacks visible germ cells in the available specimens and the connection of the paired gonopericardioducts (with high epithelium) to the pericardium could not be traced. The elongate pericardium continues termino-laterally into the pericardioducts, which have no vesiculae seminales. The pericardioducts open laterally into the spawning ducts, each of which gives rise, in continuation of this opening, to a stalked tube-like receptaculum seminis towards anterior; the receptacles then turn with their stalk anteromedially, therefore both located latero-ventrally of the beginning hindgut. The spawning ducts are glandular and paired throughout, terminally protruding within a short cone into the ventral portion of the mantle cavity (Fig. 19), where they open side-by-side latero-ventrally.

At each side, both terminal ducts of the copulatory stylet gland are short and straight; one opens ventrally into the spawning duct, the other medially (facing the spine) into the sheath of the stylets. The stylet glands are tube-like and lined by high, non-glandular epithelium; neither extends anteriorly as far as the spawning ducts. The copulatory stylets consist of a spine and, lateral to this (not ventral; Fig 19), of a gutter-like element; proximally, both are positioned within their own sheath.

In the juvenile, the pericardioducts connect anteriorly with a small mass of tissue; no spawning ducts are recognizable and no copulatory stylet apparatus is present.

Comparison: Even though the holotype is not yet mature (which may also be reflected by the absence of vesiculae sem-

inales), *Hemimenia cyclomyata* spec. nov. differs distinctly from both *H. glandulosa* and *H. atlantica* above, by the configuration of the pharynx with its striking constrictor (hence the name of the new species). Other distinctive characters include the particular morphology of the sclerites (the elongate paddle- to drop-like sclerites, Fig. 3b, being diagnostic), the unusual incorporation of the precerebral ganglia, the opening of the foregut and the configuration of the (anterior) midgut, the lateral position of the gutter element of the copulatory stylets and the opening of the spawning ducts through a short cone. The peculiar condition of the mid-dorsal keel (enclosing grooves or pits) may also be specific, but is reminiscent of the keel in *H. intermedia*, which shows a "carina with many pouches" (NIERSTRASZ 1902: 25). The lack of glands in the pre-pallial and pallial regions of *Hemimenia cyclomyata* is a feature shared with *H. dorsosulcata* and, at least with respect to the pre-pallial glands, also with *H. intermedia*; however, in addition to the body size and the geographic provenance, both these species are also distinguished by the other characters indicated above.

The second, juvenile specimen of the sample coincides in all available characters with the holotype (pharynx with constrictor and opening into the midgut, precerebral ganglia, configuration of the keel) except for the sclerite types. According to these, this specimen would represent another new species. Although some species are known to replace the types of mantle sclerites during development (metamorphosis), it remains unknown whether sclerite types (or the dominance of types) may change from juvenile to adult stage in Solenogastres. The juvenile is thus classified — with reservation only — within this species.

Familia NEOMENIIDAE Ihering, 1876

Neomeniamorpha with thick cuticle, sclerites in one layer as solid needles or spicules and elongated groove-shaped elements with or without spear-shaped

distal end; epidermal papillae generally present. Radula unknown (absent in known species); without ventral foregut glandular organs.

Genus *Neomenia* Tullberg, 1875

Type species: *Neomenia carinata* Tullberg, 1875

Definition: Solenogastres-Neomeniidae without radula, with common atrio-buccal opening; without short

harpoon-shaped sclerites; terminal sense organ and respiratory organs present.

Neomenia oscari spec. nov. (Figs 20, 22-25)

Material examined: Three specimens without keel formation (holotype, paratypes) were collected within one sample from off Galicia/Spain. After examination of sclerites, two specimens (holotype, paratype 2) were decalcified and all three animals were embedded in paraffin, serially sectioned (holotype cs. 5 μ m, others cs. 7 μ m) as well as stained with Azan by Oscar García-Álvarez. Unfortunately, the histological state of all three animals is of moderate quality; the posterior body end of paratype 2 was partly destroyed. Holotype: Banco de Galicia/Spain, Fauna Ibérica II Sta. 173A / 15 (28.06.1991): 42° 42.37' - 42° 43.00' N, 11° 47.87' - 11° 45.78' W; 760-769 m. 2 mm x 0.8 mm (section series on slides), Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (Madrid), no. 15.05/46699. Paratype 1: Same sample, animal 3 mm x 1.1 mm (section series on slides), Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, no. 103 317. Paratype 2: Same sample, animal 2.6 mm x 1.1 mm (section series on slides), Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (Madrid), no. 15.05/46700

Derivatio nominis: The species is dedicated to the author's friend and colleague in the field of Solenogastres research, Dr. Oscar García-Álvarez (Estación de Biología A Graña, Ferrol/Galicia/Spain).

Diagnosis: Animals small, up to 3 mm x 1.1 mm, body rather stout without keel. Calcareous mantle sclerites consist almost of entirely solid, slightly curved needles and some scarce other types, without spear-shaped elements distally; one pedal fold extending into mantle cavity; cerebral connectives separate; pharynx with three regions, midgut with paired terminal sack along with spawning ducts; with vesiculae seminales and receptacula seminis; anterior section of spawning ducts with dorsal pouch, ducts throughout paired, at most fusing at their opening; mantle cavity without separated genital pouch; paired stylet gland small; without suprapallial glands, 2 x 4 pre-pallial spines; 24-25 gill folds.

Mantle: The 15-25 μ m thick mantle epidermis contains several large gland cells (up to 35 μ m high) but no distinct papillae. The cuticle is between 20 μ m and 50 μ m thick. The sclerites are radially to obliquely arranged and consist mainly of solid needles in different variants ranging from 100 μ m to 800 μ m long (Fig. 20), the longer ones towards

posterior, most of them slightly curved. Groove-shaped elements (45-95 μ m long) and small elongate scales are interspersed, as are straight spines towards the rear (up to 420 μ m); small, curved scales are present ventrally (pedal groove). No groove-shaped elements with distal spear-shaped enlargement are differentiated.

Foot and mantle cavity: The roof of the pedal ciliary pit forms a single fold entering the groove and ending at the opening of the pallial cavity. The pedal glands are packed into follicles and flank the anterior pharynx. The sole glands are of the same quality as the pedal glands and continue along the pedal groove in dense arrangement; they open along the entire groove as well as pedal fold and are posteriorly enlarged (in the area below the receptacula, anterior copulatory stylets and spawning ducts). In the area below the beginning of the pallial cavity, at both sides of the terminal pedal groove, a group of four pre-pallial spines is differentiated.

The pallial cavity is spacious, its opening ending at the terminal body

Figure 20. *Neomenia oscar* n. sp., mantle sclerites (see text). Figure 21. *Neomenia simplex* n. sp., mantle sclerites (see text).

Figure 20. *Neomenia oscar* n. sp., escleritos del manto (véase texto). Figura 21. *Neomenia simplex* n. sp., escleritos del manto (véase texto).

wall. It is dorsally and laterally provided with a total of 24-26 ciliated folds in radial arrangement. The rectum opens frontally, whereas the bottom of the cavity ventral to the rectum includes the outlets of the spawning ducts (Fig. 25); the latter open axial-centrally, in the holotype somewhat protruded; the outlets themselves may be paired throughout (holotype) or fused at their opening (paratype 1). Each outlet receives the ventral opening of a small (stylet) gland and, immediately behind, there is an open connexion to the sheath of the copulatory stylets; the stylets themselves end a short distance behind at the bottom of the pallial cavity. Groups of accumulated granula strongly stained red with Azan are present at the bases of the gill lamellae in the anterior pallial cavity. These

granula do not enter the epithelium of the gill folds and thus look like deposits (concrements) rather than (suprapallial) glands.

Musculature: The circular and longitudinal fibres of the body wall musculature are loosely arranged, though no distinct ground substance or matrix is present. The circular fibres are also differentiated above the pedal groove. Beginning at the second pharynx region, a pair of small longitudinal bundles, fairly isolated dorso-laterally from the pedal groove, are present until the pericardial region.

The inner bundles of the dorsoventral musculature cause regular constrictions of the lateral midgut. In the region of the posterior pharynx, these inner bundles contribute to (and delimit) the peripheral muscle coat of the body. As

usual, the dorsoventral fibres delimit the ventral sinus below the gut. A particular longitudinal musculature is present in association with the anterior sheaths of the copulatory stylets.

Sensory system: The 140-180 μm wide cerebral ganglion is distinctly bilobed posteriorly and gives rise to the connectives separately. Three pairs of small frontal ganglia are connected with the atrial sense organ via up to $\text{\O} 20 \mu\text{m}$ thick, medullary nerves. The first ventral ganglia ($\text{\O} 60 \mu\text{m}$) lie apart above the pedal pit. A pair of elongate pharyngeal ganglia is apparently present laterally in the first region, but due to poor histology the buccal system is not reliably discernible; the buccal ganglia ($\text{\O} 60 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$) with two ventral commissures and a pair of strong dorsal nerves (dorsal commissure?) are differentiated rather latero-ventrally in the third pharyngeal region (Fig. 22). Both the ventral and the lateral body cords are for the most part medullary. The medullary suprarectal commissure ($\text{\O} 30 \mu\text{m}$) is 250 μm long and directly spans over the anal opening (Fig. 25).

In the holotype and in paratype 1, the atrial sense organ was protruded and destroyed. In the third specimen (paratype 2) it is delimited by the horse-shoe-shaped ciliary tract which forms a short but wide, unpaired ciliary plate at the roof; the short snout of the foregut is protruded into the atrio-buccal cavity. The papillae of the sensory area are single or paired and not very densely arranged. There is no distinct pre-atrial area.

The terminal sense organ is prominently formed above the mantle cavity

(Fig. 23) and is supplied with an unpaired nerve.

Alimentary tract: The alimentary tract begins dorsally in the common atrio-buccal cavity behind the posterior atrial ciliary tracts. The anteriormost portion (buccal cavity) may form a short protrusible tube or snout (paratype 2). It exhibits a 3-4 μm low epithelium in contrast to the highly cuticularised, 6-10 μm high epithelium of the anterior pharynx; neither a lip formation nor longitudinal clefts are present. The pharynx shows three regions (Fig. 22). The elongate anterior section may exhibit some bulges and is provided with a moderate circular musculature and radially arranged, subepithelial, unicellular, pharyngeal gland cells. Close to a circular fold caused in all three specimens by the adjacent sphincter region, these glands decrease in number and longitudinal muscle fibres are added. An abrupt strengthening of the circular musculature forming an elongate sphincter (40-90 μm thick) characterises the second region, whose length varies individually: only 85 μm long in the holotype (similar in length to the constrictor in *H. cyclomyata* above), 140 μm in paratype 1 and 175 μm long in paratype 2. The epithelium shows tapered cells with moderate cuticle and, again, subepithelial pharyngeal glands that open intercellularly. The short posterior pharynx is widened, provided with moderate circular as well as longitudinal musculature, and surrounded by a cellular mass which may represent follicles of elongate gland cells in a poor histological condition. The terminal portion of the foregut in all three specimens is more or

(Right page) Figures 22-25. *Neomenia oscari* n. sp. 22: Organisation of the anterior body; 23: organisation of the posterior body; 24: cross section through posterior end of midgut and gonads; 25: cross section through posterior body in the region of anal opening.

Abbreviations as in Figures 4-7, an: anal opening; mgs: midgut sack; nsl: lateral nerve cord; nsv: ventral nerve cord.

(Página derecha) Figuras 22-25. *Neomenia oscari* n. sp. 22: Organización de la parte anterior del cuerpo; 23: organización de la parte posterior del cuerpo; 24: corte en el extremo posterior del digestivo medio y en las gónadas; 25: corte en la parte posterior del cuerpo, en la región de la abertura anal.

Abreviaturas como en las Figuras 4-7, an: abertura anal; mgs: saco del digestivo medio; nsl: cordón nervioso lateral; nsv: cordón nervioso ventral.

less frontally protruded into the midgut lumen, whereby its wall is circularly overturned. There is no sphincter at this portion.

Due to the dorsoventral musculature, the midgut shows regular lateral pouches. The middorsal ciliary tract is wide (no ventral tract visible); the lumen contains numerous nematocysts and spirocysts. In the region of the end of the gonad and the anteriormost spawning ducts (opening of pericardioducts), the midgut becomes narrowed and provided with ventral ciliation. Here, a pair of ventral sacks is separated (Fig. 24: mgs). At each side the sack runs posteriorly between the copulatory stylet apparatus and the spawning duct (distal section); then, after separation of the ventral spawning duct section, the sacks run dorsally to this section (Fig. 25), posteriorly until near the opening of the ducts. These midgut sacks exhibit a flat, occasionally ciliated epithelium without a visible glandular quality. The ciliated rectum opens dorso-frontally into the mantle cavity.

Circulatory system: Only a short posterior part of the heart extends free in the short pericardium. The dorsal sinus runs, in continuation of the heart, closely above the gonopericardioducts and gonads. The ventral sinus becomes indistinct in the pericardial region. The haemocytes are irregularly round, pale cells of \varnothing 5-8 μm with distinct nucleus.

Reproductive system: The paired gonad forms a wide tube at both sides of the dorsal sinus; all three specimens are in a protandric state, with developing eggs less than \varnothing 60 μm . The narrowed gonopericardioducts are ciliated throughout and open dorso-frontally into the small pericardium, which in the holotype is filled with sperm. The pericardioducts emerge termino-laterally and show two vesiculae seminales each (Fig. 23), a short one towards the rear in the bend and a second one somewhat further in a small double-turn; these latter vesicles (Fig. 25), are voluminous in paratype 1, contain sperm and are connected by a narrow stalk, antero-ventrally to the posterior ganglion, to their pericardioduct.

The pericardioducts are ciliated throughout; proximally, up to the opening of the vesicle stalk, they show a distinct medial, heightened bolster of the epithelium. They open ventro-laterally into the anterior spawning ducts; the manifold curved stalk of the voluminous receptaculum seminis emerges frontally from each spawning duct.

Anteriorly (distal section), both spawning ducts show a dorso-posterior pouch; posteriorly, they continue as a ventral extension which runs towards the pallial cavity: Each spawning duct is accompanied along its entire length by the wide terminal midgut sack, anteriorly below the duct, posteriorly above it (Figs 24-25, mgs). The spawning ducts have a glandular epithelium with some cilia: the antero-dorsal section has low cells with some folds, the posterior-ventral section has somewhat differently staining, more glandular cells. The ducts open without any special change and differentiation (no genital papilla) axially, somewhat protruded in the holotype; the outlets themselves may be paired throughout (holotype), but are terminally fused in the 3 mm long paratype 1.

The paired copulatory stylet apparatus begins near the terminal region of the gonads proper. It consists at each side of a spine and below this of a gutter-like element. Proximally, both possess their own sheath accompanied by strong muscle bundles; the sheaths open below the spawning ducts at the bottom of the anterior pallial cavity. In the area of the anterior pallial cavity, between the terminal stylets and the terminal spawning ducts, a paired sack (75-125 μm long, 60-115 μm high, 45-50 μm wide) is differentiated; it shows a 10 μm thick, slightly glandular epithelium (Fig. 25, csg). These (stylet) glands open dorsally into the paired spawning ducts. About 10-15 μm behind this, an open ventral connection exists with the stylet sheath (facing the spine); each sheath closes up again to end shortly behind at the bottom of the pallial cavity.

Comparison: The organisation of the specimens is characteristic for the

genus. The variation in the length of the pharyngeal sphincter (second region) is unusual, but cannot be interpreted as outside the species frame (same sample), especially since no other character is distinctly correlated with the different states. Paratype 1 (3 mm) is the most mature one (voluminous vesiculae seminales, terminally fused spawning ducts). The paired glandular sacks connected to both the spawning ducts and the stylet sheaths represent the copulatory stylet gland (formerly "penis gland"); a similar small-sized gland has also been described in *Neomenia megatrapezata* and *N. trivialis* (SALVINI-PLAWEN AND PAAR-GAUSCH, 2004). Within the genus, both these latter species uniquely also coincide in differentiation of a paired terminal midgut sack. Compared with most other *Neomenia* species, the pouch of the anterior section of each spawning duct may correspond to the so-called spawning duct gland (a glandular caecum or a gland with a duct into each spawning duct), though it is here directed dorso-posteriorly and histologically not modified. Such a gland is missing only in Hemimeniidae as well as in *N. carinata*, *N. dalyelli*, *N. verrilli* and probably also in *N. microsolen*.

The genus *Neomenia* currently includes 15 described species, comparatively summarised in SALVINI-PLAWEN AND PAAR-GAUSCH (2004: Table 1). It is supplemented by a hitherto unnamed new species in GARCÍA-ALVAREZ AND URGORRI, 2003, which is diagnostically defined by the pharynx: its unique character is longitudinal clefts forming a three-part anterior pharyngeal epithelium (first region), with the ventral portion as a free lip formation ("*monolabrosa* spec. nov."); such a condition is somewhat paralleled in *N. carinata* or *N. crenagulata* (ventral cleft) and *N. labrosa*, *N. trapeziformis* or *N. megatrapezata* (lateral clefts; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; SALVINI-PLAWEN AND PAAR-GAUSCH, 2004). This region is continued by a folded foregut (regions 2-4) whose midsection is provided with a strong circular musculature and subepithelial glands cells; the opening into the midgut has a distinct sphincter.

Within the given geographic area, only the type species *Neomenia carinata* Tullberg, 1875, with a size of up to 4 cm, is known; including the variations described as *N. affinis* (Koren and Danielssen, 1877) and *N. grandis* Thiele, 1894 (see SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1997). Its distribution ranges from Lofoten and Iceland to the Strait of Messina/Italy. Based on the presence of longitudinal keel formations (and other characters), however, *N. carinata* as well as *N. trapeziformis* Salvini-Plawen and *N. megatrapezata* Salvini-Plawen and Paar-Gausch are clearly different; on the other hand, *N. megatrapezata*, *N. herwigi* Kaiser, *N. yamamotoi* Baba and *N. permagna* Salvini-Plawen are "giant" species from the south-western Atlantic or the Pacific, respectively, measuring over 10 cm; they likewise need not be considered here. With regard to the geographic provenance, all other species described from the southern hemisphere (Antarctic, Subantarctic and New Zealand waters) may also be excluded from discussion; this refers to *N. labrosa*, *N. crenagulata*, *N. laminata*, *N. proprietata*, *N. naevata* and *N. trivialis* (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; SALVINI-PLAWEN AND PAAR-GAUSCH, 2004). Thus, three species remain for serious comparative discussion: *N. microsolen* Wirén, 1892, from the Caribbean (lesser Antilles) at 293 m, *N. verrilli* Heath, 1918, from the north-western Atlantic (Gulf of St. Lawrence) at 573 m and *Neomenia dalyelli* (Koren and Danielssen, 1877) from the north-eastern Atlantic at 30-550 m (northern North Sea and Norwegian Sea, including unregistered records from June 1938 close to Iceland at 66° 20' N, 12° 28' W, 180-220 m, and 66° 27' N, 21° W, 100-150 m; up to 30 mm; Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Bruxelles).

There is similarity of the present specimens with *Neomenia dalyelli* as well as *N. microsolen*, both of which exhibit a pharynx with three regions (WIREN, 1892, SALVINI-PLAWEN AND PAAR-GAUSCH, 2004: Table 1), and with *N. verrilli*, which lacks a terminal pharyngeal sphincter; other characters, however,

such as the terminal midgut sacks distinctly separate all three species from the representatives treated herein. Despite the scant information on the organisation of *N. microsolen* Wirén, which measures 10 mm, there are distinct specific differences such as the presence of a terminal foregut sphincter and of a prominent rostral midgut caecum (WIRÉN, 1892). In addition, the rostral mantle cavity of *N. microsolen* (as in *N. dalyelli*, *N. carinata* and other species) is subdivided by a horizontal septum which separates a ventral genital pouch ("Vorhof" in WIRÉN, 1892); into this opens from dorsal the genital papilla of the terminally fused spawning ducts (WIRÉN, 1892: 48; not registered in SALVINI-PLAWEN AND PAAR-GAUSCH, 2004: Table 1). *Neomenia verrilli* Heath, with a body size of 25 mm, shows four pharyngeal regions, a dense differentiation of epithelial papillae, and posteriorly fused spawning ducts opening into a muscular genital pouch ("vagina" in HEATH, 1918), characters which contrast to the present specimens. Interestingly, *N. verrilli* exhibits similar suprapallial glands or concrements (HEATH, 1918:

209), as outlined above. The specimens at hand exhibit several characters in common with *Neomenia dalyelli*, including the differentiation of three pharyngeal regions (the lack of a separated terminal "sphincter"), a paired opening of the spawning ducts, stylet glands with outlets also into the spawnings ducts and the lack of spawning duct glands (WIRÉN, 1892, and pers. obs.). *Neomenia dalyelli*, however, grows to 30 mm and differs from the present specimens (in addition to the lack of midgut sacks and the presence of a terminal foregut sphincter, above) by the prominent and densely arranged epidermis papillae, by the fairly separated atrial sense organ, by the formation of a genital or vaginal pouch (separated by a septum) which extends rostrally beyond the proper mantle cavity and into which open from dorsal separately the spawning ducts, by the position of the terminal sense organ (in *N. dalyelli* at the posterior-most = ventral mantle edge) and by the differentiation of a paired subvaginal, thin-walled epithelial gland (SALVINI-PLAWEN AND PAAR-GAUSCH, 2004, and pers. obs.).

Neomenia simplex spec. nov. (Figs. 21, 26)

Material: A single specimen without keel formation collected from off Galicia/Spain. After examination of sclerites, ribbons of semithin serial sections (cs 2 μ m) were made with a glass blade and stained in Richardson's solution.

Holotype: Banco de Galicia/Spain, Fauna Ibérica II Sta. 173A (28.06.1991): 42° 42.37' - 42° 43.00' N, 11° 47.87' - 11° 45.78' W; 760-769 m. 1.5 mm x 0.4 mm (section series on slides), Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (Madrid), no. 15.05/46701.

Derivatio nominis: Latin *simplex* = simple, without particularity; referring to the fairly simple pharynx organisation.

Diagnosis: Animal small (1.5 mm), body rather stout without keel. Calcareous mantle sclerites predominantly of solid needles; one pedal fold, not extending into mantle cavity; cerebral connectives separate; pharynx with two regions, midgut without terminal sacks; pericardium largely above mantle cavity; with receptacula seminis; spawning ducts paired; a pair of copulatory stylets with outlet in front of the mantle cavity; without suprapallial glands,

without pre-pallial spines; twelve gill folds.

Mantle: The 6-10 μ m thick mantle epidermis bears no distinct glands or papillae. The cuticle is between 30-60 μ m thick; at some areas it shows peripheral nematocysts. The sclerites are radially to obliquely arranged solid needles (Fig. 21), most are slightly curved elements measuring up to 300 x 10 μ m, and towards posterior also straight spicules up to 250 x 9 μ m; elongate scales (60 x 13

Figure 26. *Neomenia simplex* n.sp., organisation of the anterior body. Abbreviations as in Figures 4-7.
 Figura 26. *Neomenia simplex* n.sp., organización de la parte anterior del cuerpo. Abreviaturas como en las Figuras 4-7.

µm) are interspersed. No groove-shaped elements were observed.

Foot and mantle cavity: The roof of the pedal ciliary pit forms a single fold entering the groove. The fold ends between the openings of the copulatory stylets and the pallial cavity. The pedal glands are packed into follicles and have a fairly moderate extension. The sole glands are of the same quality as the pedal glands and continue along the pedal groove; in the posterior body they are densely accumulated. They open both within the pedal fold and within the lateral epithelium of the groove.

The mantle cavity is spacious, becoming shallower posteriorly to form a groove; antero-ventrally the space continues distinctly beyond the cavity opening; the cavity is dorsally and laterally provided with a total of 12 folds arranged radially. The anus opens below the anterior pericardium dorso-frontally into the cavity; ventro-frontally a flat pouch (which may become differentiated into a short unpaired outlet) is present and receives the paired spawning ducts laterally. There are no glands around the pallial cavity.

Musculature: The circular and longitudinal fibres of the body wall musculature are loosely arranged, but only dorsally and dorso-laterally medially embedded within a structure-less, relatively thin (25-

40 µm) pale-staining matrix. There is no distinct concentration of the longitudinal fibres in the ventral body.

The moderately differentiated dorsoventral bundles cause regular lateral midgut constrictions. Below the gut, their fibres delimit the ventral sinus.

Sensory system: The small cerebral ganglion (70 µm high, 100 µm wide, 35 µm long) is terminally bilobate and gives off separate connectives. It shows two pairs of latero-frontal and a pair of ventro-frontal small ganglia which connect with the roof of the atrial sense organ via thick (Ø 8-10 µm), medullary nerves. The lateral ganglia are close to the cerebral ganglion; the first ventral ganglia (Ø 45 x 35 µm) lie laterally above the pedal pit. The buccal ganglia (Ø 40 µm; Fig. 26) show a dorsal commissure anteriorly and the usual ventral commissure posteriorly. The lateral nerve cords are almost medullary in the posterior body. The ganglia posteriora superiora (Ø 40 x 30 µm) below the anterior pericardium are connected behind the anus by a 130 µm long, medullary, subpericardial-suprapallial commissure (Ø 15 µm).

The atrial sense organ is delimited by the horseshoe-shaped ciliary tract which forms at the roof a short but wide, unpaired ciliary plate. The papilla of the sensory area are single and not

very densely arranged. There is no distinct pre-atrial area.

The terminal sense organ is at the rear of the body above the end of the pallial cavity and is supplied with a paired nerve.

Alimentary tract: The alimentary tract begins dorsally in the common atriobuccal cavity behind the posterior atrial ciliary tracts (Fig. 26). The buccal cavity proper exhibits a 3-5 μm low epithelium, in contrast to the 6-9 μm high epithelium of the pharynx which is cuticularised and in the first region longitudinally folded; neither a lip formation nor longitudinal clefts are present. The entire pharynx is indistinctly divided into two regions separated by a weak sphincter (Fig. 26) and is provided throughout with moderate, circular and loosely arranged longitudinal musculature through which unicellular, subepithelial pharyngeal gland cells open into the lumen. Midway through the pharynx is a circular fold with the sphincter, after which the pharyngeal glands are longer and more densely arranged. At the frontal transition into the midgut, the pharynx is surrounded by a circular compression fold of the midgut and connects by a very narrow opening provided with a small sphincter.

Due to the dorsoventral musculature, the midgut possesses regular lateral pouches. The middorsal ciliary tract is narrow and the terminal midgut also shows a midventral ciliation; no terminal sacks are differentiated. The lumen contains numerous nematocysts and spirocysts. The ciliated rectum opens dorsofrontally into the mantle cavity.

Reproductive system: The paired gonad forms a wide tube at both sides of the dorsal sinus and contains early stages of ovocytes. The tubes narrow posteriorly (gonopericardio-ducts) and continue dorso-frontally into the spacious pericardium. This overlies for most of its extension the pallial cavity and bears the heart anteriorly as a dorsal invagination, posteriorly as a free tube; the haemocytes are round cells of $\text{\O} 3\text{-}6 \mu\text{m}$ with distinct nucleus. The pericardioducts emerge laterally before the end

of the pericardium; they are narrow, simple ducts without vesiculae seminales. They open frontally into the simply structured spawning ducts; at the junction at each side, a small, rearward looking sacculation is formed dorsally (rudiment of receptaculum seminis). Both spawning ducts open latero-frontally into a short, flattened pouch of the anterior pallial cavity, forming a transversely wide, unpaired outlet.

The paired copulatory stylet apparatus begins laterally in the ventral half of the body in the terminal region of the gonads proper. It consists at each side of a gutter-like element and above this of a somewhat shorter spine, both which possess their own sheath over most of their length. They open below the pallial cavity at both sides of the terminal pedal fold. No prepallial spines and no rudiment of the paired stylet gland could be discerned.

Comparison: Certain features of the single specimen might be related to the subadult status of the animal; this refers to the body size, the limited differentiation of matrix, the absence of stylet glands and perhaps even of vesiculae seminales, as well as possibly to the absence of pre-pallial spines and of the paired opening of spawning ducts. Nevertheless, with respect to the presence of the copulatory stylet apparatus and when compared with not fully mature *N. megatrapezata* and *N. trivialis* (SALVINI-PLAWEN AND PAAR-GAUSCH, 2004), other organisational features of the present specimen are clearly species-specific: It differs from *N. oscari* by the mantle sclerites, the configuration of the pharynx with terminal sphincter and the outlets of the copulatory stylets at both sides of the terminal pedal fold in front of the opening of the pallial cavity. With respect to other *Neomenia* species, again only the three known northern Atlantic representatives need to be considered (see above, with *N. oscari*).

The fairly simple pharynx of the present specimen, weakly divided into two regions, contrasts with the configuration in *N. dalyelli* and *N. microsolen* with three, and *N. verrilli* with four regions

(without terminal sphincter); in comparison, such a condition appears to be independent of body size/age (see *N. megatrapezata*, and *Hemimenia cyclomyata* above). Apart from the body size, the position of the pericardium as well as the outlets of the copulatory stylets in front of the opening of the mantle cavity likewise make a difference with all three species. In addition, the rostral midgut

caecum and the presence of a genital papilla separate *N. microsolen*, whereas the epidermal papillae and the muscular genital pouch are different from *N. verrilli*; on the other hand, the epidermis papillae, the position of the terminal sense organ and the differentiation of subvaginal epithelial glands in *N. dallyelli* are in contrast to the condition in the present *Neomenia simplex* spec. nov.

DISCUSSION

The characters of the five species examined here allow particular differentiations to be recognised and thus distinct species to be defined. Certain conditions in *Hemimenia cyclomyata* and *Neomenia simplex*, however, might be related to the not yet fully mature state of the animals (body size, restricted differentiation of matrix, absence of vesiculae seminales or even of stylet glands, paired opening of spawning ducts).

Based on the combined characters of the mantle sclerites, the lack of a radula and the configuration of the accessory genital organs, three of the presented species clearly belong to *Hemimenia* within the Hemimeniidae (see definition); additional characters point to well-separated, proper species (see diagnoses and classifications). Up to now, two species were known: *Hemimenia intermedia* Nierstrasz, 1902, from Indonesia and *H. dorsosulcata* Salvini-Plawen, 1978, from the subantarctic Pacific (NIERSTRASZ, 1902, SALVINI-PLAWEN 1978). It is thus surprising that three new species inhabit East-Atlantic bottoms, and even more so that all three congeneric representatives were recorded from a limited sampling area.

With regard to the widespread Neomeniidae, only *Neomenia carinata* Tullberg had been known to inhabit West-European seas, including records from off Roscoff/Bretagne and off Llansá/Costa Brava (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1997); a more recent record of a specimen (3 cm) with a sharp "affinis"-keel comes from off Banyuls-sur-Mer/Côte Vermeille (ECOMARGE Sta. CH108

(11.6.1985) = 42° 26' 00" N, 03° 24' 10" E; 120 m; Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris). Again, it is remarkable that neither of the two new species had been found earlier, which clearly points to the lacunary knowledge of the off-shore Solenogastres fauna.

One explanation for these species being hitherto unrecorded might be the sampling depth (750 m downwards); as exemplified by *Hemimenia atlantica* (above), the new species may typically belong to the fauna of the Atlantic bathyal, not rising into the sublittoral. A second explanation involves the small body sizes of the five new neomeniamorphs, which are in the size range of meiofauna; in earlier sampling, the dredges or sleds were not provided with the necessary fine-meshed nets. In addition, as underlined by SALVINI-PLAWEN (1997), the Iberian and French off-shore fauna is poorly sampled; this is also evidenced by the more recent first record of a *Sputoherpia* species (8 mm long; Cavi-belonia-Amphimeniidae) in the same "Cangrexo I" sample as *Hemimenia atlantica* (GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ, URGORRI AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2000).

Biologically, it is difficult to explain why at least four of the five species of a closely related group (Neomeniamorpha) — two congeneric representatives of *Hemimenia* and of *Neomenia*, live together in a restricted area (off Galicia). They probably had different centres of evolution, and the main distribution area of each species possibly differs; their common existence in one area would then simply reflect marginal overlaps.

Their co-existence implies, however, sufficient specific difference to avoid species competition. Note that such co-existent distributions of congeneric species does not appear to be a rare condition within Solenogastres: Among the 85 sample sites investigated from the Antarctic and Subantarctic seas (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978), eight of them housed two to four species of a genus, particularly of *Pruvotina* Cockerell, *Rhopalomenia* Simroth and *Dorymenia* Heath (all belonging to the order Cavibelonia). This is somewhat reminiscent of the geographically co-existent representatives of the Darwin-finches (Aves-Geospizinae), in part congeneric, in the Galápagos or of the Drepanididae of Hawaii (Aves), whose various ecological niches reflect different feeding habits. We know that most Solenogastres feed on Cnidaria (see SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1981), which also holds true for the species presented herein (not confirmed for *H. cyclomyata*), yet we know little about prey species-specificity.

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Some Solenogastres species appear to feed on selected Cnidaria, such as *Rhopalomenia aglaopheniae* (Kowalevsky and Marion, 1887) on the thecaphoran *Lytocarpia myriophyllum* (Linné, 1758) or *Anamenia gorgonophila* (Kowalevsky, 1880) on *Paramuricea clavata* (Risso, 1826) (= *Muricea chamaeleon* (Koch, 1887)) and on *Eunicella* spp. Others, however, feed on a range of cnidarian prey, e.g., on Athecata (with stenoteles) as well as on hexamerous Anthozoa (with spirocysts).

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